

Sustainability through a gender lens: The extent to which research on UN Sustainable Development Goals includes sex and gender

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Making sex and gender research integral to the SDGs

- Growing recognition for the benefits of incorporating sex and gender analysis in research
- Calls for sex and gender to be integrated into SDG research
- Commitment to inclusive progress from the UN

“Incorporating sex and gender analysis into experimental design has **enabled advancements** across many disciplines...”

Tannenbaum, C. et al (2020)

“As a cross-cutting issue, **gender analyses should be applied across clusters of interdependent SDGs.**”

*International Conference on Sustainable Development
2020*

Universal Values

Principle Two: Leave No One Behind

Principle Three: Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment

UN Sustainable
Development Group

Research question

To what extent does sex and gender factor into research on the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?

Can we develop a replicable approach that allows tracking?

Our approach

Build **keyword search** to identify publications that include sex and/or gender differences in publication titles, abstracts or keywords

Identify publications that take into account sex and/or gender in each of the 16 SDGs

Build **keyword maps** for each of the 16 SDGs highlighting the areas in which sex and/or gender factor

VOSviewer
Visualizing scientific landscapes

Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman
Centre for Science and Technology Studies
Leiden University

Elsevier's SDG publication sets: <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/87txkw7khs/1>.

Read more about the mapping initiative: <https://www.elsevier.com/about/partnerships/sdg-research-mapping-initiative>

Sex and/or gender keyword search

Search Field	Search Terms	Excluded Search Terms
Title OR Abstract OR Keywords	(woman OR transgender* OR sexuality OR sexis* OR patriarch* OR neutrois OR matrimon* OR matriarch* OR maternity OR maternal* OR paternity OR paternal* OR masculin* OR intersectional* OR housewi*e* OR femini* OR {third sex} OR {men} OR *gender* OR "son preference" OR "sexual object*" OR "sex traffick*" OR "non binary" OR "human traffick*" OR "force* marriage*" OR "daughter preference" OR "child rear*" OR "sex* affect*" OR "sex* biodivers*" OR sexing OR male OR female OR childbear* OR {sexes} OR "sexual dimorph*" OR "sex* variat*" OR "sex* system*" OR "sex* select*" OR "sex* related differen*" OR "sex* ratio*" OR "sex* preselect*" OR "sex* matur*" OR "sex* identif*" OR "sex* factor*" OR "sex* extinct*" OR "sex* divers*" OR "sex* distribution*" OR "sex* disparit*" OR "sex* differen*" OR "sex* determin*" OR "sex* dependen*" OR "sex* chromosome*" OR "sex* character*" OR "sex* specific*" OR "sex* indicat*" OR "reproductive work*" OR "reproductive right*" OR "reproductive health*" OR "sex* violen*" OR "sex* harass*" OR "sex* exploit*" OR "sex* discriminat*" OR mother* OR boy OR girl OR father* OR "sex* trait*" OR "sex* health" OR "sex* behavio*r" OR daughter OR parent*) (biolog* w/3 sex) (biomark* w/5 sex) (sex w/5 stratif*)	(*engender*)
Document type	Article OR Review OR Conference Proceeding OR Short Survey OR Data Papers	
Publication Year	2015-2020	

Results

A select look at the results and maps for 2020 publications

Generally low proportions of research that considers sex or gender

Little change over time

Proportion of publications that consider sex and/or gender

SDG 5: GENDER EQUALITY

Size: appearances in publication title/abstracts
Colour: share of sex and/or gender research score

All publications:
25,601
Sex & Gender publications:
24,319
95%

SDG 4: QUALITY EDUCATION

Size: appearances in publication title/abstracts
Colour: share of sex and/or gender research score

All publications:
37,206
Sex & Gender publications:
9,302
25%

medical education

educational settings: early years to high school

tertiary education; vocational education; labour force outcomes

Limitations & Conclusions

Limitations

- Approach only captures references to sex and/or gender in **title, abstract and keyword**
 - But enables study of all Scopus-indexed records
- Here we've presented **maps depicting one year**; we recommend that those connected to SDG monitoring review multiple years
- We are limited to a view of *research* on the SDGs; further research could investigate whether **sex and gender factor into the related *policies***

Conclusions

- We have been able, through the intersection of two types of keyword approaches on Scopus data, **provided a monitoring approach for the response of the research community on SDG research**
- Laying the groundwork:
 - Contributes to evidence-based development of a roadmap toward **greater integration of sex and/or gender across research in every SDG**
 - Plus an approach to **evaluate change across each SDG over time**
- Keep **reviewing and developing the keyword search**, as research and terminology evolves

Thank you!